

Active Curiosity-Driven Object Exploration

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Our fourth work package within the ARENA project aims to investigate whether curious behaviors of children support the learning of object representations. There is a tremendous literature demonstrating curious behaviors in toddlers (Kidd et al. 2015) and the importance of curiosity for learning motor tasks (Aubret et al. 2022). However, the impact of curiosity on visual learning is poorly understood. Our approach is to develop a computational model of object learning based on an agent curiously manipulating objects.

In a first work (Aubret et al., 2023), we designed a curious agent that learns to rotate objects to maximize SLTT-based metrics quantifying a search for ambiguity or high temporal variability. We found that all the strategies found by the agent are inferior to a very simple baseline that maximizes the diversity of observed views. In addition, the strategies discovered by the model did not match the visual bias of toddlers, who learn to focus on side views of objects (Pereira et al. 2010). Our main hypothesis is that some key visual properties may be lacking when training with SLTT alone, for explaining the visual bias of toddlers.

In a subsequently published blogpost (Aubret & Triesch, 2025), we investigated the differences between visual processing strategies of toddlers and those of current state-of-the-art vision models, including SLTT. One of our main findings was that side views of objects are perceived more prototypical of an object than other views as the vision model pays more attention to the shape of the object, compared to its texture. However, assuming that this property explains why toddlers prefer the side views of an object, the prototypicality is not strong enough to match the visual bias of a toddler. Side views tend to clearly show the different features of an object as well as their relative positions. Thus, we hypothesized that side views are special because they clearly display the arrangement of parts of an object. In the same blogpost, we found that all tested vision models are insensitive to the arrangement of parts of an object, in contrast to adult humans.

Together, our studies show the intricacies of visual processing strategies emerging in toddlers relative to state-of-the-art computer vision models. In this context, the impact of embodying learning models into a curious agent will highly depend on the actual visual processing strategies of the vision model. Thus, in the next step of the project, we will study whether our recent AA-SSL model can learn to focus on the arrangement of parts of an object, when exposed to saccadic eye movements. Our intuition is that recognizing a saccadic movement from the previous and next visual features can force the model to learn to encode the relative positions of these features.

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